

D4.2.1.1 Report: Example Applications in Biomedical Research and Clinical Decision Making

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Table of Contents

- 1. Introduction..... 2
- 2. State of AI adoption in the biomedical domain 2
- 3. Definition of clinical application areas and NFDI4DS example applications 4
 - 3.1. Clinical decision support 4
 - 3.2. Medical Imaging 5
 - 3.3. Medical devices and computer-assisted surgery 6
- 4. Conclusion 6

1. Introduction

While demand for medical and care services increases, an ever-growing amount of data arises from the adoption of electronic health records and omics-based diagnostics. To maintain/improve quality of care and exploit this vast data resource for personalized therapeutic approaches within real-world settings with economic constraints, reliable automated analysis methods are imperative. Machine learning-based analysis methods have shown immense potential revolutionizing numerous disciplines. However, in the biomedical domain widespread adoption is still hindered by unique and stringent requirements. These requirements originate from the safety-critical and ethically relevant nature of many biomedical applications such as precision medicine (PM) and clinical decision support (CDS). Here, it is paramount for automated analysis solutions to gain the trust of healthcare professionals, patients, and regulatory bodies alike. Trustworthiness may be facilitated by measures such as data management consistent with FAIR principles (Wilkinson, 2016), transparency, standardization, regulatory compliance, robust risk management, and end-user education. From the methodological data analytics view, requirements to clinical prognosis and decision support models include consistency and reproducibility of predictive performance, reporting of evidence-based confidence in individual predictions, interpretability of predictions, fairness regarding existing sociological biases, and security (e.g., concerning data privacy). Correspondingly, in recent years there has been renewed interest in research areas including robust estimation of epistemic uncertainty and out-of-distribution detection, explainability in deep learning, prevention of harmful algorithmic bias, generation of faithful synthetic data, as well as privacy-preserving AI and model robustness to adversarial attacks.

In the following we give a concise overview of AI adoption in biomedical research and clinical decision making. We then define exemplary biomedical use cases including their potential impact, stakeholders, as well as existing data structures, standards, and software. Corresponding to these use cases artifacts such as datasets, challenges, guidelines, best practices, and tutorials will be provided to the NFDI4DS platform.

2. State of AI adoption in the biomedical domain

Germany is grappling with a nursing staff shortage, exacerbated by an aging population (Press, 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for innovative solutions in healthcare (Teng, 2022). The convergence of technology, artificial intelligence (AI), and electronic health records have the potential to transform healthcare delivery, addressing supply-and-demand challenges and paving the way for AI-augmented procedures and frameworks in healthcare.

To date, AI is already utilized in important applications such as medical image analysis, personalized medicine, diagnostic procedures, medical outcome prognosis, and drug discovery. It is used for virtual health assistants offering patient support and education. It extracts information from medical text and recorded audio sessions. AI-driven devices enhance rehabilitation and prosthetics.

Numerous solutions and platforms are available for AI-driven assessments conducted by physicians across a range of medical domains. In areas like brain tumor detection using multimodal MRI scans, computer-aided diagnosis systems (CADs) minimize delays in assessment, with the potential to expand physicians' capabilities (Zeineldin, 2022). IBM Watson Health offers comprehensive AI solutions encompassing image analysis, natural language processing, and clinical decision support, with applications in radiology, oncology, genomics, and drug discovery (Merative, 2022). NVIDIA Clara specializes in medical imaging, offering tools for image segmentation, annotation, and model training

(NVIDIA, 2023). Google Cloud's Healthcare API (Google, 2023) provides AI-driven tools for medical image analysis, predictive modeling, and data analytics. Additionally, Google Health licenses its Mammography AI system to breast cancer detection company iCAD (McKinney, 2020). Tempus assists oncologists in personalized treatment decisions (Tempus, 2023), while PathAI applies AI to pathology images for more accurate diagnoses (PathAI, 2023).

The AI healthcare industry is rapidly evolving, and new platforms and solutions are continuously being developed and introduced. Nevertheless, the implementation of deep learning (DL) techniques in clinical settings is constrained by certain limitations. For instance, amid the 2020 lockdown, AI's potential was recognized for swift prediction in diagnosing and forecasting the spread of COVID-19. Teams worldwide designed AI systems using algorithms trained on diverse data, from lung CT scans to coughing sounds (Mei, 2020; Laguarda, 2020). However, subsequent assessments showed that these AI-powered COVID predictors underperformed in real-world clinical settings and were limited in practicality (Wynants, 2020) due to regulatory, ethical, and technical challenges. Issues with data quality, quantity, and possible biases impacted the reliability of the AI algorithms. Ethical dilemmas arise due to sensitive healthcare data, privacy concerns, and unclear accountability for AI errors (Keskinbora, 2019). Building trust in AI among medical professionals requires addressing interpretability, reproducibility, and predictive accuracy, while standardized user guidelines and robust methodologies are crucial for establishing credibility (Recht, 2020). Despite the need for comprehensive regulation, the complex nature of these challenges requires substantial time and effort to address effectively.

Despite certain restrictions, explainable AI (XAI) is gaining traction to understand complex AI networks in the medical field (Zeineldin, 2022). However, with increasing complexity, tradeoffs between predictive performance and comprehensibility are inevitable. Recent guidelines including AI-specific extensions to SPIRIT and CONSORT, along with upcoming STARD-AI, are working to standardize medical AI reporting, aiding in sharing findings and investigating usefulness (Rajpurkar, 2022). Certain AI tools have transitioned from testing phase to deployment, garnering regulatory approval. This includes the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) supporting the integration of AI tools by providing reimbursement for particular AI systems used in medical imaging.

Investments in AI have significantly shaped the landscape of healthcare and the Medicare program, attracting substantial global funding for startups. According to Precedence Research, the global market size for artificial intelligence in healthcare reached USD 15.1 billion in 2022 and is projected to achieve substantial growth, amounting to USD 187.95 billion by 2030 (Precedence Research, 2023). Cost-effectiveness analyses of established systems, such as those developed by Google Health (McKinney, 2020), not only validate the effective implementation of AI predictors in medicine but also underscore their significance. In cancer research, AI prediction often refers to tumor discovery. Here, AI techniques improve early detection. Clinical research demonstrates consistently increased patient survival rates for cancer in recent years (Miller, 2020; Wang, 2016). Collaborative AI systems involving both human and data-driven decision-making achieve performance surpassing the capabilities of either AI or humans individually. Despite the challenges related to explainability and data availability, data based CDSS have shown promising adoption rates, particularly in countries with national health records (Sutton, 2020).

With its capacity to assist physicians in tasks such as diagnosis, risk prediction, treatment, and administrative procedures, AI leads to improved medical outcomes and patient care (Huynh, 2020).

3. Definition of clinical application areas and NFDI4DS example applications

In the following, we showcase selected use cases that serve as examples for the application of AI-driven solutions in healthcare.

3.1. Clinical decision support

Automated medical prognosis and clinical decision support systems (CDSS) are integral for efficiently accomplishing personalized medicine. CDSS incorporate vast amounts of patient-specific medical records with diagnostic, anamnestic, and lifestyle data to support clinicians in decision-making. This includes conventional and emerging novel diagnostics from the omics spectrum, such as radiologic imaging, histopathologic evidence, and biomarkers. By utilizing AI for statistical pattern recognition, AI/ML-driven CDSS can assist healthcare providers in selecting personalized therapies (Lin, 2019), optimizing drug efficacy and safety profiles (Nimri, 2020), as well as assessing and managing risk in clinical and economic concerns (Wijnberge, 2020).

Medical Question Answering (MQA) in CDSS utilizes technology and algorithms to provide accurate and relevant answers to medical queries, supporting healthcare professionals with up-to-date medical knowledge and recommendations. By leveraging natural language processing (NLP), ML and extensive medical databases, MQA systems support clinical decision-making processes (Mutabazi, 2021). For biomedical text mining, Lee J. et al. explore in (Lee, 2020) the adaptation of the language model BERT for biomedical text mining. They introduce BioBERT, a domain-specific language representation model pre-trained on large-scale biomedical corpora, which outperforms BERT and previous models in various biomedical text mining tasks. Furthermore, MQA serves as an application for examining patient-reported outcomes (Tachmazidis, 2021), where patients describe their well-being and symptoms.

For classifying medical information, coding systems were defined and standardized. The widely used international standards for coding and clinical terminology provide a systematic way of representing clinical information (SNOMED CT (Donnelly, 2006), LOINC (Forrey, 1996)), classifying diseases (ICD-10 (Krollner, 2023)), and categorizing medical procedures and interventions (OPCS-4 (NHS, 2023), ICF (WHO, 2012)), using alphanumeric codes and hierarchical system. These standardizations ensure consistency and uniformity in the way medical data is represented across healthcare systems, facilitating accurate data exchange and analysis.

With the positive trend and advancements in cancer treatment, clinical practice has expanded its focus beyond outcomes such as disease-free survival and toxicity. Cancer patients typically face increased physical and psychosocial challenges, leading to a higher probability of mental disorders (Kugaya, 2000) and a decline in their quality of life (QoL). Mental state may in turn affect tumor recurrence (Shurin, 2020; Otto-Meyer, 2019). For instance, patients who have been treated against head and neck cancer often face distinctive challenges specific to their location of cancer, like oral dysfunction, swallowing difficulties, speech restrictions, etc. (Zebralla V. W., 2021). Oral obstruction can lead to social isolation, and thus anxiety, depression, and other mental disorder (Hammermüller, 2021). The Leipzig University Clinic Department of Otolaryngology developed OncoFunction; a system to collect data on the condition of patients during aftercare (Zebralla V. M., 2020). The study collected clinical coded information from medical professionals as well as mental and physical data from patient-reported outcomes of more than 1000 patients over a period of 7 years. The dataset includes patient reported outcomes on physical and mental state, clinical parameters, and lifestyle variables. Within the NFDI4DS project, we will employ laryngeal cancer treatment and follow-up use cases based on data provided

by OncoFunction for developing educational material and best practices regarding data-driven clinical decision-making and prognosis. These include predicting the symptomatology and mental state of a patient following a specific therapy, as well as assessing the impact of mental state and symptomatology on tumor recurrence, and vice versa. In doing so, we put a special emphasis on AI trustworthiness in the sense of explainability and estimation of predictive uncertainty.

3.2. Medical Imaging

DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) (Martin, 2001) is a widely used international standard for digital diagnostic imaging, storage, and clinical communication across medical imaging systems and software. It stores medical image data (pixel information and metadata) from various modalities including X-ray, MRI, CT, and U/S. Combining DICOM's standardized format with radiomics' advanced analytical techniques offers valuable insights for personalized medicine, disease characterization, and treatment response prediction. Siemens AI Rad Companion exemplifies an AI-powered radiology platform that enhances workflow efficiency and diagnostic accuracy through automated measurements, segmentation, and abnormality detection in different imaging modalities.

Numerous studies have shown that AI algorithms surpass traditional approaches when it comes to analyzing medical images, such as X-rays, MRIs, and CT scans (Esteva, 2017; Ardila, 2019; McKinney, 2020). In the realm of medical image analysis, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have emerged as a potent AI technique (Kaur, 2021), demonstrating their effectiveness in image classification (Campanella, 2019; Esteva, 2017), segmentation of the region of interest (Ranjbarzadeh, 2022), and anomaly detection (Barua, 2022; Lin, 2019). CNNs play a pivotal role in applications such as fracture detection (Kuo, 2022; Kim, 2018) and tumor identification (Kaur, 2021; Arabahmadi, 2022), leveraging their capacity to learn intricate patterns and features from high-resolution images, resulting in precise and efficient outcomes. The architecture of the model allows CNN to automatically learn hierarchical representations directly from the raw pixel data. CNN has been extensively used in medical studies, that depend on image interpretation, such as radiology (Wu, 2020; Ouyang, 2020) and pathology (Jackson, 2020; Laleh, 2022). For instance, in (Ardila, 2019), a CNN was created to predict lung cancer risk using CT scans, highlighting better performance in early detection than radiologists.

Within the scope of the NFDI4DS project, and considering the established standards for digital diagnostic imaging, we are expanding our efforts towards creating AI-based solutions for segmentation, classification, and anomaly detection in hyperspectral imaging (HSI) during surgical workflows.

HSI shows promise in preoperative cancer detection and post-cancer removal assessment for tumor-free resection margins. HSI analyzes tissue-light interactions, revealing specific spectral signatures, enabling discrimination between various tissue structures and assessment of tissue perfusion (Sersa, 2022; Clancy, 2020). Previous studies have used support vector machines (SVMs), random forest (RF), logistic regression (LR), and CNNs for analyzing HS image data in detecting various cancers (Liu, 2022; Aboughaleb, 2020; Fabelo, 2018), and ongoing research explores different pre-processing (Martinez-Vega, 2022), architecture (Halicek, 2020; Hong, 2021), and post-processing approaches (Li, 2022) to enhance artificial networks.

To acquire the HS image data of resected colorectal tissue, the commercial push-broom TIVITA[®] Tissue device (Diaspective Vision GmbH, Am Salzhaff-Pepelow, Germany) was used. We possess HS data cubes of 56 patients that were annotated by experienced pathologists and surgeons using comparison with histopathological slides. Our goal is also to create a highly configurable open-code framework for HSI using modern software architecture approaches, where it would be possible to work with different HSI

datasets and combine them. To date three colleagues and eight students successfully worked on this system with colorectal, esophagogastric, brain, pancreatic tumor and pancreatitis (both ex-vivo and microscopy data). The data is used to develop convolutional neural network models for automatic tissue segmentation.

3.3. Medical devices and computer-assisted surgery

Alert systems have gained widespread adoption across various domains to mitigate human errors, benefiting both experts and non-experts. Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) often employ alerts, an automated "second line of defense" strategy to notify clinicians of potential errors. This approach entails the automated analysis of the majority of cases, while cases characterized by uncertain or conflicting evidence are identified and referred to healthcare professionals for review (Chien, 2022). Consequently, this process contributes to the enhancement of evidence-based care, an improvement in safety measures, and a notable decrease in overall workload (Kinlay, 2021). Studies have confirmed the effectiveness of alerts in reducing medication errors (Bepko Jr, 2009) or as an early warning system (Wijnberge, 2020). Additionally, the integration of alert systems in surgery robotics (SR) and Intensive Care Units (ICUs) improves surgical procedures and patient care. Intelligent decision support systems in surgery provide valuable assistance throughout the surgical process, utilizing algorithms, ML, and real-time data analysis. These systems identify patterns, anomalies, and promptly alert healthcare providers for timely intervention (Attanasio, 2021). SR platforms like the da Vinci Surgical System enable minimally invasive procedures directly in the ICU, offering enhanced precision and dexterity (Peters, 2018) with improved patient outcomes and reduced complications (Da Vinci, 2022). To summarize, robotic systems in intensive care represent a valuable assistance, enhancing precision, patient care, and workflow automation. Robotic ventilators (Bazdyrev, 2021; Malik, 2021), drug dosing and delivery systems (Bepko Jr, 2009), mobility, and rehabilitation robots (Ferre, 2021), as well as sterilization and infection control robots (Zhao, 2021), are examples of how SR positively impacts intensive care settings. Integration of SR and automation technology promises to revolutionize intensive care, further improving patient outcomes and reducing errors (Randell, 2015).

While the majority of healthcare robotics research has traditionally focused on areas such as surgical interventions, robot prosthetics, and rehabilitation robotics, the demand for robotics and automation in intensive care settings is growing due to its potential to address staffing shortages and enhance patient care (Teng, 2022; Randell, 2015). To ensure safety and quality management of surgery monitoring and robotic systems, the internationally recognized Service-oriented Device Connectivity (SDC) standards (Besting, 2017) encompass the transport mechanism and device model (Core standards), safety device connection (Participant Key Purposes), and specifications for medical device classes (Device Specialization). Additionally, the SDC family is complemented by the IHE profile SDPI (Service-oriented Device Point-of-care Interoperability), further refining use cases and standards.

4. Conclusion

AI has the capacity to profoundly reshape and optimize medical practice and healthcare delivery. However, in the medical domain, its widespread adoption is hindered by ethical and safety-critical concerns regarding predictive uncertainty, trustworthiness, comprehensibility, sociological bias, and regulatory issues. The report at hand presented short overviews for three AI applications areas and

specified corresponding specific use cases. These use cases are exemplary for the benefits, challenges, and pitfalls of data-driven solutions for the medical domain.

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